

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PEER CORRECTION IN TERM OF SENTENCE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Correction is widely seen in education as essential for both encouraging and consolidating learning, and this importance has also been recognized by those working in the field of second language writing. This study is conducted in an attempt to investigate the effectiveness of peer correction on students' writing ability with the main focus on sentence structure. In order to achieve the desired aim, in a class at HUFU, the researcher conducted an action research in which 40 students' writings were carefully examined. During two months, the findings on student writing analysis provide the researcher with a satisfactory answer on peer correction as the finding results proved that peer correction really brings the effectiveness to the development of students' writing skill. In general, most the students can point out and correct the mistakes quite well. Besides, they have a positive attitude towards peer correction in improving their writing ability and would like to apply it more in the future. However, there are still some aspects which this paper has not gone through. The researcher has sketched out some recommendations so as to help the later researchers cover this topic with deeper and broader consideration for future studies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement

Correction plays an important role, especially to language teaching and learning writing, in motivating learning because it informs learners about the degree of their learning or their needs for improvement. The development of writing skills depends mainly on the responses that learners receive through their writings. In his research, Beach (1989, p. 127) pointed out that teachers put deliberate efforts in correcting students' compositions, hoping that their correction can help students to make good progress: "The immediate, short-term goal of responding to writing is to help students revise and improve a particular paper. Beyond that short-term goal, the ultimate, long-range goal of response is to help students learn to critically evaluate writing on their own". Despite the teacher's meticulous comments or corrections, learners tend to consider the marks only, paying little or even no attention to their papers. Indeed, Selinker (1992, p. 150) claimed that errors are indispensable to learners since the making of errors can be regarded as "a device the learner uses in order to learn". As a result, there is a need for students to recognize the importance of errors which occur in their writings, to fully grasp and understand the nature of the errors made. This assumption has held the researcher in high regard for what English teacher can do with the intention of helping students make use of their own efforts at writing meaningful texts

in the target language. Peer correction seems to be the answer to this question for peer correction helps students discover whether they communicate their ideas successfully or not and encourages them to revise and improve the texts they produce (Paulus, 1999). Moreover, Hyland (2003, cited in Chiu, 2008) viewed peer correction as a powerful method because it helps to improve students' critical thinking of writing and evaluation than the traditional teacher response. However, despite the significant role of peer correction – especially its great effect on students' writing revision, there still has been limited studies or researches on peer correction compare with the outnumbered studies on traditional correction method – teacher correction. In the light of that, this article aims to examine the use of peer correction in writing class, that is, the effectiveness of peer correction in sentence structures. To discuss this issue, at first, a brief overview of writing as well as peer correction is presented. Next, students' papers collected in the action research would be closely inspected to find out the conclusion. Finally, there would be some discussion on the pros and cons of the study and some recommendations for further researches as well.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptions of Writing

There have been numerous definitions of writing by many researchers. As for Canale and Swain (cited in Silva & Matsuda, 2002, pp. 252), writing was defined as “a manifestation of, as well as the process of manifesting, sociolinguistic, strategic and grammatical competences mediated by the use of orthographic systems”. Byrne (1988, p.1) defined writing as “the act of forming graphic symbols, which are arranged according to certain conventions to form words and words have to be arranged to form sentences”. From a different point of view, Lannon (1989, p.9) gave a definition of writing as “the process of transforming the material discovered by research inspiration, accident, trial and error, or whatever into a message with a definite meaning- writing is a process of deliberate decision”. According to Tribble (1996, p.3), writing in language teaching and learning is viewed as a “language skill” which involves “not just a graphic representation of speech, but the development and presentation of thoughts in a structured way”. Furthermore, writing was also defined as a social process by Candlin and Hyland (cited in Phung, 2004, pp. 107): “Writing is an engagement in a social process, where the production of texts reflects methodologies, arguments and rhetorical strategies constructed to engage colleagues and persuade them of the claims that are made”. However, Tribble (1996, pp. 3), in language teachers' viewpoints, stated that writing is “a language skill which is difficult to acquire”. It “normally requires some form of instruction” and “is not a skill that is readily picked up by exposure” (Tribble, 1996, pp. 11). Additionally, writing is also “a process that occurs over a period of time, particularly if we take into account the sometimes extended periods of thinking that precede creating an initial draft” (Harris, cited in Phung, 2004, pp. 10). More to the point, Byrne (cited in McDonough & Shaw, 1993, pp. 184) put it that language teachers need to make students fully aware that “any piece of writing is an attempt to communicate something; that the writer has a goal or purpose in mind; that he has to establish and maintain contact with his reader; that he has to organize his material and that he does this through the use of certain logical and grammatical devices”.

Conceptions of Peer correction

Peer correction (also known as peer response, peer feedback or peer review) is known as the process by which students exchange constructive criticism on their critical reading, writing, and speaking skills. Liu and Hansen (2002, p.75) considered peer correction as “the use of learners as sources of information and interactants for each in such a way that learners assume roles and responsibilities normally taken on as formally trained teacher, tutor, or editor in commenting on and critiquing each other’s drafts in both written and oral formats in the process of writing”. Many researchers have highlighted a great number of advantages which peer written correction brings to students’ revision as well as their writing skill. Among these advantages, Villamil and Guerrero (1996, p. 65) argued that a remarkable aspect of peer correction is “affectivity,” which includes “camaraderie, empathy and concern for not hurting each other’s feelings”. In the same line, Mendonca and Johnson (1994, cited in Rollinson, 2005) discussed peer audience tends to be more sympathetic than the more “distant and possibly more judgmental” teacher audience. In terms of students’ attitudes, students themselves find the peer correction experience ‘beneficial’ because they can avoid some certain mistakes next time and learn many things based on the way their peers correct their writings. In his study, Zamel (1985, p. 97) demonstrated clearly a way the peer editor could help the writer to develop the quality by providing the reader’s point of view:

The reader can discover the underlying meaning and logic of what may appear to be an incoherent text and instruct the writer how to shape, modify and transform the text; the writer can simultaneously discover what lies behind and motivates the complex reactions of the reader and help the reader understand a text that up to this point may have been ambiguous, elusive, or unintelligible.

In addition, Bartels (2003) concluded in his study, peer correction could help to create the feeling of being an audience for both the writers and the peer readers. Unlike oral correction, peer written correction could bring students many opportunities for “communicative writing”. In other words, by giving and receiving peer written correction, the students can freely express their desire to provide useful comments and the students can show their aspire to create better writing versions next time. Above and beyond, Bartels (2003) emphasised that students could have many opportunities for “instant correction and negotiation of meaning” thanks to peer written correction. They could request clarification, ask questions and even argue about their peers’ comments which can lead to more language learning. This advantage of peer correction was indicated to bring the improvement in students writing skills as that: “...the more the revision process can be learned as an interaction between writers and their readers, the more L2 learners will fully appreciate the functions, savor the fruits, as it were, of their newly acquired writing proficiency” (Chaudron, 1984, p. 16). In terms of response and revision benefits, Rollinson (2005) explained that peer writers can revise effectively on the basis of comments from peer readers. Rollinson (2005) aslo claimed that becoming a critical reader of others’ writing may make students more critical readers and revisers of their own writing. Furthermore, he listed out some benefits of peer correction since peer correction operates on a more informal level: “Peer correction may encourage or motivate writers, or at least provide a change from the more one-way interaction between the teacher and the student, where student may end up making revisions

without necessarily agreeing with or even understanding the teacher's authoritative comments... The writer receiving comments from peers retains the right to reject comments, and is thus more able to maintain the possession of her own texts" (Rollinson, 2005, p.25). Another benefit from peer correction is that peers can have much more time providing correction on their friends' writing than their teachers (Rollinson, 2005). In agreement with this idea, Caulk (1994, cited in Bartels, 2003) pointed out that the teachers often do not have enough time to provide their students with thorough comments on each paper in large classes while peer respondents can provide their friends with thorough ones by reviewing writings in many different aspects.

Though peer written correction has many advantages, it has its own shortcomings. It is understandable because peer written correction is a very complex process that requires training and structure in order to be effective, both in L1 and L2 classrooms (Villamil & de Guerrero, 1996). Chaudron (1984), in addition, found that the influence of peer and teacher correction on writing improvement to be about the same, while Zhang (1985) even drew out that teacher correction was more effective for improving grammatical errors than peer or self-correction. Some problems with peer correction are specific to the L2 situation. Keh (1990) suggested that student editors, for instance, are more probably to deal with surface errors than problems of meaning. An important consequence is that, inexperienced or low level L2 students may find it hard to judge the validity of their peers' comments or correction (Leki, 1990). Lastly, it cannot be denied that peer review procedures also take up much of the classroom time.

3 OBJECTIVES

Many researchers have carried out many researches to find out whether peer correction has influence on students' writing revision, and there have also been many different results as mentioned in the previous section. This contradiction between the authors and the results about peer correction has challenge the researcher to conductan action research in the context of her class in HUFU. The purpose of the research is checking the effectiveness of peer correction in writing with regard to students' development writing ability, mainly focusing on sentence structure.

There would be some predicted obstacles which the researcher has to face against and overcome. The literature leads the conclusion that the effects of peer comments on revision is not a simple cause and effect matter, but rather a complex one, dependent upon the interrelationship of multiple factors within the social environment. In some cases, some students would be unwilling, ill-advised, or even unable to follow peer correction in revising and reproducing their own papers. Therefore, some of the students would show to benefit from the comments of their peers while some others do not. The researcher would keep this prediction in mind that the reality can be quite different from what she expected so as to avoid idealizing L2 peer written correction as sites of constructive interaction. An important factor in the success of peer correction seems to be student training, with instruction encouraging a greater level of engagement with the task and more helpful and concrete advice (Keh, 1990).

4 RESEARCH QUESTION

All things mentioned above urged the researcher to carry out this study to further understand the effectiveness of using peer written correction among students and more importantly, to find out whether or not peer correction could affect students' revision and writing skill. This article is a tentative study with the aim of addressing the following question: Does the peer correction really help students improve their writing ability?

5 METHODOLOGY

Subjects

There are 15 students (9 are female), who are members of a general English course taught by the researcher, participating in this research. Because this was a small-scale study, this number of subjects seemed to be reasonable and manageable. All of them are at the age of 19 years old. All are elementary learners with Vietnamese as their mother tongue. However, some students have a lower or higher one, so they have different levels of writing skill as well.

Instruments

This study employed textbook 'Paragraph Essentials: A Writing Guide' by Linda Wong (2002) which consists of seven step approaches for writing effective paragraphs. It was chosen because it matched the students' level of English. Moreover, there were clear, concise but detail steps to help students produce a good paragraph.

To process the collected data, descriptive statistics method was used. Students' mistakes were mechanically counted. Forty writing assignments were analyzed to see the differences by counting the mistakes made in terms of sentence structure only, including topic sentences, fragments, run-ons and comma slices. After that, all the findings were presented in graphs and charts – a friendly way to easily compare different variables in the same category as well as better illustration and explanations to student's improvement when they used their peer written correction to revise their own writings.

The students were highlighted to pay more attention to the quality than the quantity of their writing. They were also brought to the light of the benefits which peer correction brings to their learning when they apply peer correction in revising and improve their own writings. The first assignment would get teacher correction and students had to resubmit after that to compare the results. The second and the third one would be completed with the help of peer correction. The teacher would collect the assignments to observe, compare with the first one and find out the results. The last assignment would be done by individuals in class with no peer written correction. The teacher would have a chance to examine and affirm the results received with the help of these final assignments.

Students were asked to write small paragraphs within 100-200 words only. The topics of paragraphs in student writing assignments collected for analysis were as followed: "Your favorite place", "A place you want to visit", "Your typical day", and "Your dream vacation".

Procedures

The study was set in a class in HUFI where writing - one of the four important English skills was being taught in 6 periods per week during 8 weeks. The aim of this class was to enable students to write a descriptive paragraph. Peer written correction was also introduced to students and used in this class.

To prepare for the research, in the first week, students were taught how to write a descriptive paragraph. At the same time, they were also trained how to produce a good topic sentence as well as recognise and avoid fragments, run-ons and comma slices. In the second week, peer correction was introduced to students. The teacher pre-trained the students to evaluate a written work as well as how to give and make the most of peer correction on writing effectively. The teacher carefully presented the procedure in which students' writings would be commented and rewritten by using peer correction. The teacher also provided students with some guidelines, a list of correction symbols (see appendices) and; especially, a paragraph checklist (see appendices) to help students apply peer correction effectively.

The main procedure of the research could be viewed as following steps:

First, students were assigned to write the first paragraph with the topic on "Your favorite place". In class, students were taught to brainstorm, make outlines, and write the first draft. The teacher would provide help if required. The assignments were completed at home and handed in the next class. Then, the teacher would return the papers with detailed teacher correction back to students and the students had to reproduce the paragraph (with the same topic) and submit in the following class.

Second, students were introduced to the peer correction, which included its steps, goals and benefits as well as the roles of readers and writers. The teacher reminded students that the readers need to be supportive of the writer while the writers had to be ready to receive some negative comments. "A place you want to visit" was the second topic assigned to students. In class, students become involved in activities such as: brainstorming, outlining, drafting, analysis and discussion through peer correction. After making drafts, students engaged in pair to have an opportunity to act as readers with the purpose of challenging and negotiating meaning during discussion. In their peers, they could help each other to develop the idea by giving examples, or pick out the gaps in understanding and suggest some changes in the organization which caused confusion. The teacher could support students immediately during class-time or later in break-time by guiding students to work out the solution to some problems they cope with while practicing peer correction. However, this help was judicious. Students then used the comments to adjust their own drafts and finished the assignment at home.

Third, "Your typical day" was the third topic which students had to cover. This topic also went through the same procedures with the second topic; however, in this time, students had to do one more peer correction with the outputs besides the drafts. In other words, the students would first work in class on their drafts, then finished the assignment at home, conducted peer correction on the products in the next class, and; at last, perfected their final product to turn in the next meeting.

After peer correction activity, the whole class discussed the correction in group through some communicative discussions because communicative discussion was also a necessity to provide students with chances to share their experiences and understand more about each other.

In order to post-test the effectiveness of peer correction in improving the student’s writing ability, students had to write a paragraph on the topic “Your dream vacation” and submit in class. There would be no students’ peer correction this time but only the teacher correction examined the writings.

Data Collection and Analysis

The results point out that peer reviewers can make good suggestions for sentence structure and mechanics while they have many difficulties in helping their friends improve the topic sentence. This can be explained by the fact that the topic sentence is always one of the most difficult points in writing paragraphs because there is no fixed answer and one topic can be addressed and discussed in different ways.

STUDENTS' IMPROVEMENT FROM 1ST TO 4TH ASSIGNMENTS

Generally speaking, with the effect of peer written correction, students of different levels of writing proficiency made different changes in their writing assignments. As the chart shows, it can be concluded that nearly all students belonging to different levels of proficiency tend to benefit from peer correction although levels of effectiveness varies. Within the researcher's prediction, low-proficient students made more mistakes which were easy to point out and correct or make suggestions for revision. In short, though peer correction was not the only component causing the changes in students' writing versions, it could not be denied that it was one of the most significant and effective factors that helped students find it easier to revise their writings and feel more confident to turn in their papers to their teacher.

6 DISCUSSION

Merits

According to the findings as well as the personal observation, this study did gain success to some extent. First, peer correction is proved to be useful in helping writers to receive feedback on ideational aspects of their writing such as more ideas and different points of view. Second, when involving in peer correction, peer responders have much time to practise more; and consequently, be better in grammar. Peer correction provides students with chance to make reflection through reading their friend's writing; at the same time, the students can notice that they may make the same mistakes as their peers made. In other words, peer correction does not simply give students chance to comment or correct his or her partner's drafts, but it also alerts self-awareness to them. In this step, the students' role are worked as 'mistakes searcher' and this role makes the students more critical on their own writing. Third, there is; undeniably, a great amount of interaction that appears during peer correction. This interaction can help students to express their meaning freely and easily. They are able to clarify and negotiate between the writers' meaning and the readers' understanding. Last but not least, concerning students' perceptions of their peers' written correction, there are many positive attitudes and high appreciation of peer correction from students. A high percentage of students state that they can generally improve their writing skill due to peer correction on writing. Moreover, most of them also agreed that peer correction help them to revise more effectively and avoid mistakes next time they create a piece of writing.

Limitations

Although the research question was addressed and the study objective was achieved, there still exist some inevitable limitations in this study. First, this research was conducted for a short time, two months with 33.75 contact hours. Additionally, this research is absolutely a small scale one with the involvement of only 15 subjects with 40 writing papers. Second, only one methodology – action research and only one data collection technique – documentation were applied in the study. Besides, the study examined only on students' assignments to measure the effectiveness of peer correction. These are shortcomings which hold the researcher back from getting more precious findings related to peer correction. Consequently, it is probably impossible to investigate the breadth and the depth of the addressed question. Lastly, the most notable problem happened when some students did not welcome their partners' correction. This is well-matched with what Ferris (2002) reported because students "do not believe that someone who is also in the process of learning the target language is capable of making worthwhile comments" (p.103). It was Rollinson's advice (2005, p. 26) that helped the researcher overcome this problem: "many students may need a significant amount of initial persuasion of the value of peer correction, since they may not accept the idea that the peers are qualified to take on the role of teachers and critique their writing".

It is highly advised that future studies should be conducted with longer time, broader target subjects, and the addition of some more supplemental methods as well as examining more aspects of the question. What is more, other researchers who are interested in peer correction can broaden

the scale of the study either to cover another kind of correction, that is, peer oral correction or to take a close look at the consideration between peer correction and teacher correction. Last but not least, further studies can focus on the teachers' perception of peer written correction on their students' writing and their support activities to enhance the current situation.

7 CONCLUSION

The findings of the study have proven that peer written correction plays a vital role in helping students revise more effectively and improve their writing ability in most cases. The use of peer correction aims at helping learners become more critical of their own texts was employed successfully in this research. When students listen to their peers' points of view on what they have written and have the chance to rewrite their writing, they are also exercising the ability to detach themselves from their papers and read it with the target reader's eyes. In addition, with the primary assistance of the checklists, students become familiar with the aspects of discourse which are central to the communicative power of their texts and little by little gain more confidence so as to become more autonomous revisers of their own texts. Therefore, peer correction is surely an instrument which can be an essential part of any English writing classroom. To conclude, through this study, peer written correction has proved itself to have a positive impact on students' revision in particular and their writing ability in general. In order to enhance the betterment of writing teaching and learning, both teachers and students should take peer correction into consideration and put it into practice more and more.

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APPENDICES

PEER CORRECTION SHEET

- Your partner's assignment title _____
- Your partner's name _____
- Your partner's name _____
- Your partner's student number _____

Evaluators

- Your name _____
- Your student number _____

1. Read the text to find out your partner's ideas.

2. What did you like about your partner's draft?

3. Are your opinions similar to or different from those of your partners'?

4. Does the draft have sufficient length? If not, what should be added?

5. Is the draft well-organized? If not, how should it be reorganized?

6. Tell your partner which part caused trouble in understanding the content?

7. What would you like to suggest so that your partner can improve the draft?

PARAGRAPH CHECKLIST

CRITERIA	Yes	No
Paragraph Content		
1. Does the paragraph have a topic sentence?		
2. Does it clearly introduce the main idea?		
3. Does it hook the reader's interest?		
4. Does the introduction preview the topics that will be covered to support the main idea?		
5. Does the paragraph have at least three supporting details?		
6. Does the paragraph have a concluding sentence?		
7. Is the meaning of each sentence clear?		
Paragraph Format		
1. Does the paragraph have a title?		
2. Is the paragraph in dented?		
3. Is the paragraph with in margins?		
Grammar and Punctuation		
1. Does each sentence begin with a capital letter?		
2. Does each sentence end with punctuation?		
3. Are all the words spelled correctly?		

CORRECTION SYMBOLS

Take time to look at the following examples carefully. You will have to use these symbols when giving comments to your friends' papers.

SYMBOL	DEFINITION	EXAMPLE
SP	Spelling	The woman has eihgt children. The woman has eight children.
P	Punctuation	We go to school everyday__ We go to school everyday.
C	Capitalization	I love to speak english . <i>I love to speak English.</i>
WW	WrongWord	He lives at Vista. <i>He lives in Vista.</i>
^	AddaWord	You should speak to ^ teacher. You should speak to the teacher.
X	Take Out a Word	Do you go to the work? <i>Do you go to work?</i>
SV	Subject/VerbAgreement	She live in a big house. <i>She lives in a big house.</i>
VT	VerbTense	I go to the beach yesterday. <i>I went to the beach yesterday.</i>
AG	Agreement	Three boy went to school. <i>Three boys went to school.</i>
?	Unclear Meaning	She likes very today . She likes to play tennis every day.
→	Indent	This is the first sentence in a paragraph. This is the first sentence in a paragraph.
WO	Word Order	They went yesterday to school. <i>They went to school yesterday.</i>
WF	Wrong Form	She is a beauty woman. <i>She is a beautiful woman.</i>

SYMBOL	DEFINITION	EXAMPLE
SF	Sentence Fragment	<p>Because I was tired. I went to bed because I was tired.</p>
RO	Run-on	<p>He walks to school and because of the big school he gets lost but he likes it. <i>He walks to school. The school is big and sometimes he gets lost but he likes it.</i></p>
CS	Comma slice	<p>I never enjoyed reading comic books when I was a child, fantasy novels were always my favorite. I never enjoyed reading comic books when I was a child; fantasy novels were always my favorite.</p>